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The Perspective on Child in Turkish Society in Terms of Childhood Sociology

Çocukluk Sosyolojisi Bağlamında Türk Toplumunda Çocuğa Bakış Açısı

ABSTRACT

In this study, to understand the value and meaning given to children in Turkish society, an 8-question interview was applied to 31 people. The answers obtained from the interviews with open-ended questions were analyzed. The purpose of using a qualitative method is to capture all answer possibilities. The results are meaningful to show us not only the child's perspective but also the Turkish family structure. We have also understood the role of mother and father in the home, the difference in perspective between girls and boys, and the influence of religion and traditions on the formation of values related to the child. The results of the study enable us to understand the intergenerational transformation of the perspective given to children by the Turkish society, since interviews were conducted on the people at the various age range. The findings make an important contribution to the debates in child sociology. At the same time, in the historical development of the meaning attributed to the child, we can understand how the child is looked at today. As a result, while the older generations take the issue of having children as an obligation of traditions and religion, younger generations take the issue more emotionally. Older generations take the children as the main factor in establish a family, on the other hand, younger ones do not accept having children as a basic element of a family establishment. Additionally, in the context of gender, older generations have stated that the predominant responsibility for raising children often falls on the mother. On the other hand, younger generations take responsibility for both mothers and fathers with a more egalitarian approach. While the older generation and middle-aged people look at the concept of childhood as a more sacred, abundant, and work force at the same time, the younger generation approaches the concept of childhood more critically and cautiously. Basically, the reason for this is that the two generations who grew up in different social structures have different views and preferences.

Keywords: Childhood Sociology, Perspective on Child, Family.

ÖZET

Bu çalışmada Türk toplumunda çocuğa verilen değer ve anlamı anlamak amacıyla 31 kişiyle 8 soruluk görüşme uygulanmıştır. Açık uçlu sorularla yapılan mülakatlarda elde edilen cevaplar analiz edilmiştir. Nitel yöntem kullanılmasının amacı, tüm cevap olasılıklarını yakalamaktır. Sonuçlar bize sadece çocuğa bakış açısını değil aynı zamanda Türk aile yapısını da göstermesi açısından anlamlıdır. Anne ve babanın evdeki rolünü, kız ve erkek çocuklar arasındaki bakış açısını, din ve geleneklerin çocuğa ilişkin değerlerin oluşumundaki etkisini de anlamak mümkün olmuştur. Araştırmanın sonuçları, çeşitli yaş aralığındaki kişilerle yapılan görüşmelerden oluştuğundan, Türk toplumunun çocuğa bakış açısının nesiller arası dönüşümünü anlamaya olanak sağlamaktadır. Bulgular çocuk sosyolojisindeki tartışmalara önemli katkı sağladığı gibi. Aynı zamanda çocuğa yüklenen anlamın tarihsel gelişimi içerisinde günümüzde çocuğa nasıl bakıldığını da göstermektedir. Sonuç olarak yaşlı nesiller çocuk sahibi olma konusunu geleneklerin ve dinin bir gereği olarak ele alırken, genç nesiller konuyu daha duygusal bir şekilde ele almaktadır. Daha büyük kuşaklar aile kurmanın temel unsuru olarak çocukları görürken, daha büyük kuşaklar çocuk sahibi olmayı aile kuruluşunun temel unsuru olarak görmemektedir. Ayrıca toplumsal cinsiyet bağlamında, yaşlı kuşaklar, çocuk yetiştirmede ağırlıklı sorumluluğun çoğunlukla annede olduğunu belirtmişlerdir. Buna karşın genç kuşaklar daha eşitlikçi bir yaklaşımla hem anne hem de babaya sorumluluk yüklemektedir. Yaşlı kuşak ve orta yaşlılar çocukluk kavramına daha kutsal, bereketli ve aynı zamanda emek gücü olarak bakarken, genç kuşak çocukluk kavramına daha eleştirel ve temkinli yaklaşmaktadır. Temelde bunun nedeni, farklı sosyal yapılar da yetişen iki kuşağın farklı görüş ve tercihlere sahip olmasıdır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Çocukluk Sosyolojisi, Çocuğa Bakış Açısı, Aile.

1. INTRODUCTION: THE CONCEPT OF CHILD AND CHILD SOCIOLOGY

Childhood emerges as a concept that forms the basis of human beings. The place of the individual in social life begins in childhood and in this process, he achieves social gains. In addition to the biological existence of the child, good upbringing, development and education are of great importance. While childhood is considered a long process, it is seen as a process that starts from fertilization and continues until puberty. The important difference between children and adults is that their physical, physiological, behavioral and psychological characteristics are still in a developmental process and they are constantly growing and developing. The fact that the child completes this development in the best way and starts to gain social experience basically starts in the family. The family is in an important position for the child to continue his life in a healthy way and to be thrown into the outside world. When children grow up in a peaceful environment, their personalities are shaped more positively. Being a mother and father is not just a biological contribution, it prepares the child for the outside world in an environment of love and trust and can continue to exist next to the child in a way that he can stand on his own feet. Children who cannot grow up in a safe family environment also feel insecure in the social world. Basically, children who are deprived of this sense of trust can falter in the outside world and be thrown to different places in different ways. Children who cannot get a foundation in the family have to come face to face with social life directly. Examining the social position of the child in social life is very important in terms of "Childhood Sociology". Although the concept of childhood did not seem like a sociological research topic at the beginning, the phenomenon of childhood began to take its place as a sociological research topic with the thought that childhood should not be handled with a single point of view and the relation of childhood with other institutions should be taken into consideration. In line with the content of the study, it is examined and revealed how the child is positioned, how childhood progresses in the historical process, and how the child's place in the family and social life is met. What is childhood? What distinguishes children from adults? Are children influenced by adults? Are children seen as a biological necessity, or are they considered within a social structure? Questions like these show themselves in every society. As long as societies exist, these questions will naturally continue to be asked. The answers to the questions may vary depending on the structure of the society. In order to answer these questions, it becomes clear that there are many scientific perspectives about the child (Şen, 2011: 5). Childhood actually has a very important place as it is the period that shapes the future lives of individuals and creates their characters. People actually take the behaviors that prepare their current lives from childhood.

In addition, the attitudes of the individuals in the society to the child, the place of the child in the society and the family, and how the child develops in time are also related to the situation. Childhood is a time when an individual develops both physically and cognitively. Childhood, in which the world of imagination is active with active and new ideas, is also a period of relationships. The places where children grow up have an important place in their reintegration into society. When children grow up in a peaceful environment, their personality is shaped accordingly. The perception of childhood has witnessed different events since past societies. From the bad times when nearly half of the children were killed and the name of a child who lost his life was given to his sibling, to the days when children were not seen as separate from adults, a more free childhood emerges from the child who is seen as a work force to the child who socializes with school.

The family factor is the basis of the phenomenon of childhood and opinions about the child. How the family has changed with social change over time, changing family models also have an impact on childhood and give it a new meaning. In society, children are seen as good individuals, a factor that serves as assurance and kinship relations in interstate agreements. The meanings attributed to childhood have also changed with the Renaissance, which enables the understanding of the value of the individual. The factor that distinguishes children from adults is that they are "innocent beings". With the increasing acceptance of the fact that children have a private life, it has become clear that childhood has a unique life world (Uğur, 2018: 228).

Children are born into life as social beings. It begins to contain many concepts in it. The cultural values in the family and the structure of the society in which the child is born directly affect the child. Children adopt the cultural characteristics they receive from society and establish relationships. They will always look to be useful to other people with the instinct of achieving success in life (Yıldırım, 1997: 124). It is children who shape the future of society. How children are brought up is important in this respect. For backward societies, this is nothing. It is possible to be a spectator to the treatment of children such as bad words and violence. Being a child in such societies, rooting for children's rights is one of the biggest investments made for the future of society. When the child starts school life after a while, a relationship of

trust should be established with the teacher, and a supportive environment should be formed by itself. The environment of the child shapes the future, and futures create new societies.

The concept of childhood should not fit into a certain age range. Although children under the age of eighteen are legally considered children, every adult has a childhood in which they cannot live emotionally. A seventy-year-old grandfather can exhibit childlike behaviors in a thirty-five-year-old uncle. Therefore, childhood can continue in any adult. Childhood was viewed as a slightly more comfortable life. Because you don't have a big responsibility, your only job is to play games, have fun. Adults forget all the world's bustle that they unite and play the old games. It is possible to define that moment as childhood.

When we look at today's Turkish society, although the conditions are different from time to time, the child is generally valued. What is meant by these conditions is the socio-economic conditions of the family. If a family's economic situation is good, the child is brought up in a more stress-free way. In addition, there is a good education. Families who lead a luxurious life for their children also ensure that they receive a good education. However, if the economic situation of the family is bad, the growth conditions of the children also change. Many psychological traumas occur in children. The situation is not just about the economy. Although there is no financial problem in wealthy families, spiritual problems may arise. Generally, children who grow up in such environments may face problems such as a lack of love and indifference. Here, too, there is spiritual deprivation. In fact, the important thing is to provide a peaceful environment for children in any situation, regardless of material and spirituality. This is the primary duty of parents. Children should live their childhood in the best possible way. It is the families who are aware that the past years will not come back.

The child is the building block of a society. The social environment is also important in the socialization process of the child. In particular, the family has an important effect on the child in the transfer of social norms and values. The child becomes the mirror of the society in which he lives in the family. The family that exists within the society can be called a small society. In order for society to progress in a healthy way, it passes through regular families. In today's modern societies, the family institution is experiencing great difficulties. It offers unwritten rules to people who exist in society. Rules are taught to children from the age of two, which is the age of socialization of each parent.

From a certain time, the child begins to guess what he should or should not do in the society in which he exists. When we say the society in which he exists here, first of all, his family and relatives constitute him. A child who has difficulty learning the rules or who is not taught may experience negative situations both in his school life and in his other social life. Here, both the environment and the behavior of the family are important for the child. Because the child's psycho-social development period is based on imitation. The child begins to direct his life by imitating his environment. By thinking it's a child, he doesn't understand", the one-to-one negative states and movements made next to him are recorded by the child's brain. As a matter of fact, parents can catch their negative behaviors in the behavior of the child. They may even react by getting angry with their children. Usually, the parents do not find the fault on themselves, stating that the child has acquired these wrong behaviors from his friends.

The child may attempt to apply every situation that he/she has witnessed and learned in his/her family or social life. He does this with his actions or words. For example, the father who speaks bad words in the family reminds the child of swearing, and the child who has grown up with violence reflects the violence on his friends. In general, if he has seen positive behaviors from his family, he reflects it positively, if he has witnessed negative events, he reflects it negatively on his environment. Therefore, when parents teach something to the child, it should be looked at first whether it is a behavior according to the parents or not. Whatever is expected from the child, his life should be directed according to those situations. Although it may seem easy to raise good children or to help them have character while bringing them to a certain age, it is quite a difficult task.

It is necessary to draw attention to the denied features of childhood, to determine how to improve the social order, and to refer to the sociology of childhood for a basic thought on children's rights. As another factor, Western societies have an understanding of children. In these societies, it is accepted that children are separated from politics. Children are isolated in kindergartens, family and similar places (Güçlü, 2016: 6,7). Children can be the subject of politics, but they should not be included. How can it offer children a better society? How can they maximize their education? How can they effectively conduct interactions with families? Your questions must be heavy. Politically, children can be made better, or the possibility that children may be harmed should be taken into account.

Child sociology, which progresses independently from anthropology and morphology, child science (psychology, psychiatry, pedagogy, etc.), child law and mainstream sociology, has a large share in the expansion of child and childhood research. It can be said that the children's rights movement has taken on the task of a compass after the second half of the 20th century, as much as the intensification of its researches and the social and political construction of the child (Şirin, 2019:18). With this understanding, the ideas of a holistic view with children have emerged in societies. In this respect, child sociology has facilitated the display of children's rights in a more comfortable way. Children are a subject that cannot be limited to social sciences. Therefore, deep issues such as child history, culture, philosophical context, on the other hand, the political construction of the child by the state are of interest to societies.

Children's sociology is an issue that has not been taken into account for a long time. The reason for this is the result of the complex interrelation of two historical situations with the epistemological (positivism) and ontological (holistic) approaches of the 19th century and important social, economic, cultural and political transformations such as the French Revolution and the Industrial Revolution. It is revealed that the curiosity of sociology to explain modern societies is neglected not only in children but also in adults (Gürdal, 2013:4). The reason for this can be related to the fact that societies do not pay attention to children. Adults who think that children do not have a place in the social dimension have kept the child in the background. The child can affect the economy, politics and culture of a society. With modernization, the importance of the new child is understood more. By trying to bring the child to the fore in sociology, it reveals its place and importance in society.

With these modern sociological approaches, children have the opportunity not only to shape their own lives but also to influence the society they live in. This child-centered modern sociological approach criticizes traditional socialization approaches in two ways. First; It is the progress of both socialization and developmental psychology approaches with a homogeneous view as if all children are in the same social conditions (Güllü, 2015: 85). However, every child is born in a different culture, geography, different economic conditions and different gender. There are many differences such as the meanings that societies ascribe to children according to their gender, the reflection of the culture they belong to, and ethnicity. Therefore, it would not be correct to look at children from a single point of view.

A second criticism is that children are evaluated as passive beings that can be shaped by adults and the way they affect society is left in the background (Güllü, 2015: 85). The most important point is to highlight the forms of influence on society. Society shapes its economy, culture and geography thanks to children. It will not be right for the progress of societies to throw the child into a second plan.

In the context of childhood sociology in Turkey, the West is taken as an example. This West is actually a discursive West and it can be said that it encodes itself as an ideal with an orientalist discourse. In the sociology of childhood, the West and Europe can discursively consider itself as an unproblematic upper culture. By dismantling this order, colonizing countries such as France, Belgium, Netherlands, England and Spain left important social problems to countries other than their own (Ördem, 2020: 4472). Türkiye has been influenced by Europe. Most of the academic studies in Turkey were written by being influenced by the West. Since Turkey's exchange of ideas with the West officially started with the Tanzimat, it has come to the present in a more comprehensive way. When an assessment is made of the perspective of children according to Western societies, this situation can both cause a crisis and be perceived as a social progress. Here you may be faced with a dilemma. Taking an example can affect both the child and the society both positively and negatively.

The concept of child emerges as a concept that is important for all societies but is not taken into account. Just as children affect society, society affects children. While parents are raising their children, their own views are actually ingrained in the child's mindset while the child is growing up. Parents transfer right or wrong to children according to their own ideas. When a child is born, the first society he encounters is his family. The family reintegrates their child into society for a while. Afterwards, the child starts to become an individual after the age limit of eighteen determined by the society. Whether this age limit is right or wrong varies from person to person. Age may differ in each society, but before the child can be an individual in himself. The phrase "you will understand when you grow up", which is common in Turkish society, has very deep meanings. The child, who is the responsibility of his family to a certain extent, is faced with life one day. In order to understand the concept of child more broadly, it is necessary to understand how the child was received in past societies.

2. CHILDHOOD IN HISTORICAL CONTEXT

Childhood is not only a biological condition, but also a concept with social and cultural roots. Throughout history, it is seen that the perception of childhood has quite different meanings in different geographies and different time periods according to societies. It is not possible to give a single definition of childhood. Society shapes children according to their priorities. The society's view of the child progresses in parallel with the sense of justice. The child comes to society as a defenseless and powerless individual and continues to exist in this way for a long time. From a psycho-social perspective, adults who see themselves as great also include situations such as seeing children as weak, managing them, and feeling themselves valuable compared to children (Dirican, 2018: 41, 42).

Defining and understanding the childhood of the child correctly and examining the stages he has gone through in the historical process will contribute to the formation of happier children and therefore happier societies by eliminating wrong practices and attitudes towards children (Sağlam & Aral, 2016: 45).

Primitive societies were nomadic and had to kill animals to get their food. Therefore, in order for the children to adapt to these conditions, they should not be sick or weak. In fact, as this situation changed over time, weak and sick children were left to die. In primitive societies, there is a distinction in terms of gender. Girls were killed because they could not provide as much labor as boys (Erkut et al., 2017: 19). The fact that the boy is seen as stronger and dealing with external affairs more makes the man stand out. This is a factor of inequality that also exists in current societies. The point of view of "men are superior to women", which is subconscious from past societies, continues to exist in Turkish society as an example. Turkish society, which has a traditional structure, sees the boy child ahead of the girl child. The girl child is perceived as an individual who mostly deals with housework, cleaning, and needs to be in the kitchen all the time. This naturally affects girls. He is compelled to do the work attributed to him. Here, first of all, it is necessary to change the idea structure of the society before the family. Changing the thoughts of one or two families does not mean that all individuals that make up the society change. Society should act together to make its power more efficient on children. It is necessary to find solutions from the city to the families in the most extreme village. Because when a person acts differently, he can affect other individuals who make up this society, indirectly, if not directly. It can be faced in many ways such as psychological, physical and spiritual.

Antiquity appears to be a period when an adult was common. Children were not of interest to adults. When we look at Ancient Rome, we see that the family is an important concept. At this age, only precocious wonder children, i.e. those who "think like the elderly," were of interest. In this age, the family has an important place in the education of children. In this period, the church recommended discipline to the parents in the education of the child and remained silent to the absolute authority of the father over the child. The Romans loved to pass on the culture of culture to the child. However, the boy was taught the law of the twelve plates. Children's perception of play; In studies conducted in different parts of the world, different toys made of stone, bone, wood and dough have been found. In ancient times, there are playgrounds in the city centers, games drawn on the walls in the interior, sculptures and visuals of children playing (Canlı and Demirarslan, 2020: 62).

There are certain distinctions about childhood in ancient times. There are certain differences between children born at this age. It has been observed that children who are not wanted before or after birth are abandoned by the opinion of the father, who is the head of the family. The father leaves when he realizes that he cannot raise his children when he sees a certain ailment or a disability of the child (Senol et al., 2012:645). Here, it is seen that the economy had an effect on children even in the Ancient Age. Although families gave birth to their children, they could easily leave them alone. The impact of the economy on the child is clearly evident. Compared to modern societies, the effect of this factor continues, but unlike families, if their economic situation is not good, they do not want to give birth to children rather than abandon them.

When we look at the education on children in ancient times, it is seen that the boy is at the forefront. The schools that the child would attend and the education he would receive were determined by his father. The distinction brought about by the economic situation emerges in the Ancient Age about education. Another striking point is why the mother does not have any say. The order established through the father in everything naturally leads to conflicts. The problem is not only that there is no exchange of ideas between parents. The idea structure of the society and the economic situation shape the families. Inequality should not be imposed only on families. Because the factors that push families to those situations are obvious.

It is seen that religion was influential in the understanding of childhood in the Middle Ages. The dark developments of the period left their effects on children. In the Middle Ages, the child is seen as a piece of property as a result of the ideology of goods and slavery, which is exposed to bad behavior. At this time, children are considered as individuals who do not have an effect on reproduction and do not fulfill an economic function.

The religion factor draws attention in the understanding of children in the Middle Ages. The church justified the negative image of the child on the basis of original sin, and the child seen as a sinner was despised. The way to be cleansed from sins is baptism of the child. According to the Christian religion, children are born with a bad temper. Since they cannot protect themselves from bad events, they must surrender to God and be punished for being born with a bad temper (Öztürk, 2017: 260). The duty of families here is to destroy these evils. In this way, families were taught that it should be done through punishment, and the children were subjected to a constant discipline.

In this period of gender discrimination, girls now deal with the natural household chores, while boys work in the fields and with artisans, either choosing to be soldiers or starting a religious life.

Another factor is early marriages. While the age of marriage for boys is fourteen, girls are only twelve. In this period, families should have five or more children during their marriage, but if the death rate is high, they should have two or three children. The striking factor in this period was religious views. Religion is shaped in the context of the meanings it imposes on the child. Oftentimes, in foreign TV series, movies and even foreign films about war, situations such as the baptism of the child actually come into our mix, but we cover this situation implicitly. The sanctions that people applied to children on religion at that time should not be ignored.

Childhood in the Middle Ages was almost non-existent. In this period when the difference between the sexes was sharpened, if the child was a boy, he was considered a baby until the age of five, and as the adult man of the family after the age of five. From this age on, children dressed in the same way as adults, and their duties and responsibilities were seen as adults. In fact, there were cases of showing infants and children sexual acts, and sometimes adding them to these acts. It is seen that the child joins the society at an early age. It draws attention that children are not treated like children when they are only five years old and their consciousness is just starting to settle down. It will be easier to look at this situation on the negative side. Because in the current society, when these are communicated to anyone, most people will not comply with this situation. It is obvious that most people will reject these events without separating boys and girls. It can be said that childhood ends early in the Middle Ages, but childhood is explained for longer periods compared to modern society.

The lack of a childhood awareness in the Middle Ages does not mean that children are not valued, that they are not given sufficient closeness, and their needs are not met. The fact that children are not aware of their unique characteristics, developmental stages, and children's life that distinguish them from adults has led to the failure of a separate childhood period to emerge. Therefore, the love given did not exist in the present sense. Here we can evaluate the concept of time. The time devoted to children was very little in the Middle Ages due to social conditions. It is also possible that children may seem worthless because families cannot spend time with their children. It would not be right to perceive it as a period in which the child is not wanted all the time. The duties and responsibilities that society imposes on adults have distanced them from their children or are the main factors in the religious rules that are adhered to.

In Modern Age, the new world order that emerged after the Middle Ages also shaped a new understanding of childhood. Along with science, nation, state and religious freedom, childhood as both a social structure and a psychological condition was formed in the 16th century. In this new order, the sum of economic, social, political, religious, cultural and social conditions are the building blocks of this new understanding of childhood (Öztürk, 2017: 256-264).

When we look at the historical processes, every age and every period has its own unique understanding of childhood. In addition to these understandings, new attitudes were needed. While children could not find much value in the past, they become individuals who find value in society with modernization. In past ages, adults show a view of the world from a single window. Although children do not affect society, there is a world where boys find value. Religious views dominate, and it seems rare for children to find value compared to adults.

In today's modern society, the consciousness of the child is more important than the feelings of the children. In order to raise the child, the understanding of the development of the child's cognitive structure

is increasing. Because children are important for the construction of society. Now, the thought in the modern world is that children will shape the future of the world. In today's world, the definitions of the child are handled with a perspective that includes sociological, biological, physiological and psychological definitions, evaluates the child's individual characteristics and environment as a whole, and attaches importance to his developmental characteristics and rights.

One of the important ideas about how childhood was created in a social framework proposes an explanation for the Enlightenment period, which is much more limited to a concrete invention brought by the period, rather than the spirit of the period and the changes it initiated. The modern understanding of childhood also argues that the idea of childhood, which is considered one of the greatest inventions of the Renaissance, began with the separation of the adult from the child, as a result of adult information based on the printing press (Akbaş et al., 2009: 97). Since the Middle Ages, children have gradually started to create their own worlds more and more. The influence of adults on the child still persists, but its influence has waned. Children are also affected by the families they belong to, but they also know that they have a freer life. The age in which childhood undergoes a significant change is the present modern society. The point of change is that children become more aware of themselves. In past ages, children were acted as slaves of adults. Many rights of the child have been ignored.

3. METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH

Eight open-ended questions were asked to a total of 31 people, 12 men and 19 women, and in-depth interviews were conducted. The questions asked of the participants are:

- 1: Do you prefer a child as a girl or a boy?
- 2: How many children should be in an ideal family?
- 3: What does having a child mean to you?
- 4: What does it take to raise a good child?
- 5: How to raise good children?
- 6: What should be the duties of children towards their parents?
- 7: Should the child be asked when making decisions in the family?
- 8: Does the responsibility of raising the child fall mostly on the mother or the father?

The oldest of the participants is 85 years old and the youngest is 20 years old. The age range of the participants was kept wide. Obtaining the perspective of individuals of all ages shows how intergenerational perspectives and care for the child have changed. It is advantageous to keep the age range wide in order to understand the intergenerational change in the meaning attributed to the child. The marital status of the participants is also important. In order to ensure that both married and single people are represented, 19 married 12 single participants were interviewed.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the questions asked and the answers given to the participants, we are shown how more children are positioned from the perspective of Turkish society. It is possible to categorize the answers of the participants, in which individuals from all walks of life are addressed, with their common and different aspects. Especially when the Turkish family structure is taken into consideration, there are more common points in the answers of the individuals who are experienced in this subject and have children. In the answers given by the elderly individuals based on their experiences, there are answers given by adding the traditional elements of the Turkish family structure and the phenomenon of religion. If we evaluate the general answers of the older population, the idea that the mother element is more effective on the child than the father is dominant. At the same time, we can see the thoughts that the child is brought up with religious elements and that many children are necessary for fertility and the continuation of the lineage. In particular, in the answers of some participants, the idea that children should be taken care of as well, in return for the effort they give, is dominant among the duties of the child when they are in need of care. In today's society, this fear is quite high in elderly individuals. Because in modern society, with the emergence of individualization along with the nuclear family structure, the aging parents are not taken care of within the family, including the traditional Turkish family society structure, and they are more left in nursing homes and are condemned to live alone, considering the solution of the problem not spiritually but

materially. For this reason, the elderly people think that they do not get the reward of their efforts for their children, and they think that their debt of loyalty is not fulfilled.

Another factor that we can consider in common in the answers given by the participants is that they want more children and that girls are more loyal and beneficial than boys. The basis of this idea actually comes from the traditional family structure. In the old days, while the girl child was seen as an unwanted, weak and surplus property, with the advancement of age, the girl is seen as auspicious because she is more related and close to her family than the man. As mentioned before, in today's modern society, the fear of being alone is more dominant in today's modern society, so the good of the child is now seen better. For this reason, it is also seen in the answers of the participants that the girl child is more beneficial. Another factor that is especially seen in the answers of the elderly and middle-aged people is the idea of prioritizing the mother in the role of caring for the child. Especially since the mother element is considered sacred in the Turkish society, the idea that children are more fond of mothers is dominant. In the analysis of the answers, on the other hand, because the father is more distant, the children are not fond of the father, and at the same time, the father is far from the domestic responsibilities to meet the economic expenses of the house and the duty of raising the child spiritually. For this reason, the idea that raising the child falls mostly on the mother is dominant. This idea is more common especially in traditional societies such as Turkish society. For example, in Western societies, the awareness that parents have common responsibilities is more developed than in traditional societies. Because in Western societies, both parents can provide material and spiritual duties together. In Turkish society, the task of raising children in the modern period also looks at economic power. The answers of the participants generally appeal to families with moderate economic status. In families with high economic status in modern society, besides the parents, as a third alternative, help is taken from elements such as caregivers or child nurseries, private schools, private lessons from an early age in order to better raise the child and receive education. Generally speaking, economic power is also important in raising a child, as well as parents. In a middle-class family, if the father did not have to work, perhaps because he could have the opportunity to spend more time with his child, the answers would be different from the thought that only the care falls to the mother.

In the analysis of the answers of the youth, besides the traditional answers such as middle age, the social point of view is more evident. In the question "How many children should ideally be in the family?", there was no one child answer, but there should be at least two and at most 4-5 children. The idea that the child should grow up as a sibling and that he should know the feeling of sharing and brotherhood is dominant. In fact, this is an indicator of transmission from generation to generation. Because in today's society, while individualism and career are at the forefront, the idea of having a child with the employment of women in business life remains in the background. However, as an idea, if you still have a child, knowing the feeling of fraternity, it is suggested in the answers to have at least two children rather than one child. This shows us that no matter how much modernization takes place, our cultural structure still exists somewhere. Since the young people have not yet adapted to the business life economically, they have looked at the upbringing of the child more spiritually. Because they are the children of their parents, they expect spiritual interest and love from their parents before material things in the family. This is reflected in the answers of the participants. One of the common points of middle age and young people is the thought that the care of the child somehow falls on the mother. However, young people think and are aware that this is the result of necessity. They think that there is such a perception in the structure of Turkish society, but that the responsibilities fall not only on the mother, but also on the father. Because young individuals experience this situation in the family, they give their answers by taking their share, but they think that they should be raised under equal conditions when they become parents.

According to the content of the study, in the analysis of how the point of view is from generation to generation and to the child, it is seen that the young people are affected by the cultural structure and thought of the older people. However, it is seen that the young people express their thoughts by blending traditional and modern elements. In general, there are similarities between generations in the idea of the child's place in society. Because the child takes the family as an example first. Afterwards, the traces of the family are seen in his thoughts and behaviors, no matter how much he mixes with the society. Especially in Turkish society, which has a traditional social structure, having an extended family structure allows it to see many generations together while growing up. This shows us in the answers of the participants that no matter how much the child grows up in a modern society, he carries traces from the family and generations.

The study aims to examine the child, childhood, the historical process of childhood, family, and child, and the place of the child in society. When we look at the concept of a child in general, there are ready answers in societies. Childhood has not been processed deeply, and its importance has only just begun to emerge. In

this respect, the processing of the concept of childhood in the content of the study fills an important place in the literature. In the content of the study, the general expressions, the conceptual explanation of childhood, how it is positioned in society and what kind of perspective it has on the child are discussed. The concept of the child is not only a biological entity but also how it is in a social position and what kind of responsibility is given to childhood conceptually. How do social structure, family relations and other factors affect the child's growth and development? It is generally covered in the study. Since childhood is an important period in the development of the individual, which determines how they will be in their future lives, sociological analysis is also important. Childhood is a period in which the individual develops both physically and biologically. One of the most important elements in the upbringing of a child is the family. The family strengthens the foundation of the child and prepares the child for social life in his later years. The upbringing of the child, getting a good education and meeting his material and moral needs pass through the family institution. The family institution, which can show cultural differences from society to society, instills the society and culture that it has adopted into the child. There have been changes in the environment in which the child is raised, as many changes from the past to the present modern era have led to transformations in the family institution. While the child adopted the cultural and traditional elements more in the old times with traditional structure, in today's modern society, it has turned into the individual attitude and the development of the child in the modern society structure. For this reason, especially in today's modern society, there is a conflict between generations about raising children. While the old generations are raising their children with more traditional methods, the new generation is raising their children despite the structure of the modern period, so there are different perspectives between generations. This is basically the element that is also addressed in the content of the study. It is desired to determine similar and different aspects of the perspective of the participants of different ages and different generations on childhood. While the older generation and middle-aged people look at the concept of childhood as a more sacred, abundant, and work force at the same time, the younger generation approaches the concept of childhood more critically and cautiously. Basically, the reason for this is that the two generations who grew up in different social structures have different views and preferences. The common aspect between the two generations is to have more than one child in the family and to learn about fraternity. In the content of the study, the inferences we will make in general, in the answers received in line with the questions asked to the old generation, the thoughts that the positioning of the child should be a good son, that the children should be taken care of in the future, that they were seen as a workforce because there was a need for labor power in the old times were determined. The younger generation, on the other hand, criticized the wrong aspects of the view on childhood in their view of the concept of childhood and expressed their own thoughts on how it should be. In the content of the study, it was seen that there were inferences in line with the hypotheses, and it was determined that the perspective on childhood was different between the two generations.

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